

Documentation of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting system 9

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Contributors

MÉTÉO-FRANCE

Damien SPECQ

Laurent DOREL

Jonathan BEUVIER

Constantin ARDILOUZE

Lauriane BATTÉ

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Change Log

Version	Date	Description
v1	2024/12/31	First submission
v2	2025/07/11	Final version: adjustment of the 1st real-time forecast date

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1. Executive summary

Météo-France has been involved in real-time seasonal forecasting activities since the late 1990s, and in operational production of seasonal forecasts for the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) since 2017. This document provides the technical description of the 9th version of its seasonal forecasting system, in operations since 1 May 2025. System 9 is an updated version building on the two preceding systems 7 and 8, respectively released in 2019 and 2021, and documented in Batté et al. (2019) and Batté et al. (2021).

Section 2 of this report provides a brief overview of the new system, while Section 3 describes in detail each model component, including the main novelty which is the NEMO 4.2 ocean model coming along the SI³ sea-ice model. Section 4 is dedicated to the initialization strategy, for which a similar initialization strategy as in System 7 is used. Section 5 is dedicated to the ensemble generation strategy, which is similar to System 8. Section 6 provides an overview of the workflow procedures, from initialization to post-processing.

2. Basic facts

Table 1 below provides the main features of Météo-France System 9.

	Météo-France System 9
Ensemble version	
Ensemble version identifier code	CNRM-CM 6
Short description	Global ensemble system using a lagged-average and a stochastic scheme to take into account initial state and model uncertainties. Based on 51 members, run once a month up to 7 months.
Status	Operational
Date of the first forecast run	01/05/2025
Configuration of the EPS	
Is the model coupled to an ocean model?	Yes from day 0
Short description of the ocean model	NEMO v4.2 ORCA 0.25° grid, 75 vertical levels
Is the ocean coupled to a sea-ice model?	Yes
Short description of the sea-ice model	SI ³ , embedded in the ocean model. SI ³ includes 5 ice categories and an adaptive elastic-viscous-plastic rheology.
Is the model coupled to a wave model?	No
Horizontal resolution of the atmospheric model	TL359 (~ 50 km)
Number of atmospheric model levels	137
Top of the model	0.01 hPa
Type of model levels	Hybrid sigma-pressure

Forecast length	7 months
Run frequency	Once a month
Is there an unperturbed control forecast included	No
Number of perturbed ensemble members	51
Integration time step	Atmosphere/surface: 10 minutes Ocean/sea-ice: 15 minutes Coupling frequency: 1 hour
Initial conditions and perturbations	
Data assimilation method for analysis	ERA5T data assimilation (4DVar including variational bias correction) Ocean and sea-ice initial conditions are provided by a stand-alone NEMO4.2 - SI ³ run forced by ERA5 and nudged towards GLO12 analysis from Mercator Ocean International
Resolution of the model used to generate Control Analysis	TL639L137 (ERA5) for atmosphere ORCA 0.25°, 75 vertical levels for ocean
Ensemble initial perturbation strategy	Lagged initialization and in-run atmospheric perturbations
Model uncertainties perturbations	
Is model physics perturbed?	No
Do all ensemble members use exactly the same model version?	Yes
Is model dynamics perturbed?	Yes (Batté and Déqué 2016)
Are the above perturbations applied to all forecast members?	Yes
Surface boundary perturbations	
Perturbation to sea surface temperature?	No

Perturbation to soil moisture?	No
Perturbation to surface stress or roughness?	No
Any other surface perturbation?	No
Other details of the models	
Description of the model grid	Reduced Gaussian Grid
List of model levels	From top to bottom (Pa) 1, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 16, 22, 29, 38, 49, 62, 78, 97, 119, 145, 175, 210, 249, 293, 343, 398, 460, 529, 604, 687, 777, 875, 982, 1097, 1221, 1355, 1498, 1651, 1813, 1987, 2171, 2366, 2572, 2789, 30178, 3258, 3511, 3776, 4053, 4343, 4645, 4960, 5286, 5626, 5977, 6342, 6719, 7112, 7520, 7945, 8388, 8851, 9335, 9842, 10371, 10924, 11502, 12105, 12735, 13392, 14077, 14791, 15534, 16309, 17116, 17955, 18829, 19737, 20681, 21662, 22680, 23738, 24836, 25976, 27157, 28382, 29652, 30967, 32329, 33739, 35199, 36709, 38271, 39885, 41554, 43278, 45059, 46897, 48795, 50750, 52757, 54803, 56877, 58968, 61066, 63162, 65244, 67304, 69330, 71316, 73253, 75134, 76953, 78705, 80386, 81993, 83524, 84977, 86352, 87650, 88871, 90017, 91090, 92092, 93026, 93895, 94702, 95451, 96143, 96783, 97374, 97919, 98420, 98881, 99305, 99695, 100052, 100379, 100679, 100954, 101205
What kind of large scale dynamics is used ?	Spectral semi-lagrangian
What kind of boundary layer parameterization is used ?	Cuxart et al. (2000)
What kind of convective parameterization is used ?	Gueremy (2011), Piriou et al. (2007)
What kind of large scale precipitation scheme is used ?	Lopez (2002)
What cloud scheme is used ?	Sommeria and Deardorff (1977)

What kind of land-surface scheme is used ?	Explicit multilayer snow and soil scheme (Masson et al. ,2013; Decharme et al, 2019)
How is radiation parametrized ?	ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016)
Re-forecast configuration	
Number of years covered	32 years (1993-2024)
Produced on the fly or fixed re-forecasts ?	Fixed re-forecasts
Frequency	monthly
Ensemble size	31 members
Initial conditions	<p>Atmosphere and land surface initial conditions are interpolated from ERA5 (Herbsach et al., 2020)</p> <p>Ocean and sea-ice initial conditions are provided by a NEMO 4.2 - Si³ simulation forced by ERA5 and nudged towards GLORYS12V1 reanalysis from Mercator Ocean International https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021</p>
Is the model physics and resolution the same as for the real-time forecasts?	Yes
Is the ensemble generation the same as for the real-time forecasts?	Yes

Table 1: Description of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 9.

3. Modeling components of the forecast system

3.1 Introduction

Météo-France System 9 is based on the CNRM-CM global coupled climate model developed in the climate modeling group at CNRM (Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques, Météo-France & CNRS, Toulouse, France). The model components of the CNRM-CM version used in System 9 are indicated in Figure 1.

Real-time seasonal forecasts and past seasonal reforecasts (also called hindcasts) are both computed with CNRM-CM runs on the Belenos and Taranis supercomputers at Météo-France.

Figure 1: CNRM-CM components of the Météo-France seasonal forecasting System 9. Adapted from Voldoire et al. (2019).

3.2 The atmosphere model ARPEGE-Climat v6.5

ARPEGE-IFS forecast model has been jointly developed by ECMWF and Météo-France for numerical weather prediction since the late 1980s (Courtier and Geleyn, 1988). A climate version of this model (ARPEGE-Climat) was specifically designed at Météo-France for climate change and seasonal predictability experiments by Déqué et al. (1994).

System 9 builds on the physical parameterization schemes developed for the CMIP6 version of the CNRM-CM model (Voldoire et al. 2019), for which the atmospheric component ARPEGE-Climat version 6.3 is described in more details in Roehrig et al. (2020). Several developments since the publication of CMIP6 have led to changes in ARPEGE-Climat, such that the current version used for System 9 is version 6.5. Compared to the referenced version 6.3 from Roehrig et al. (2020), the version of ARPEGE-Climat in System 9 has the following modifications:

- Changes were made to the implementation of the surface momentum flux due to orography based on Beljaars (2004).
- Improvements to the code were included for better water conservation, subgrid-scale variability of surface fluxes, and turbulence in stable cases.

- The radiation scheme for both shortwave and longwave has been changed to ecRad (Hogan and Bozzo, 2016).

Note that the change of the radiation scheme is also the only significant atmospheric change between System 9 and the previous System 8. In System 9, ARPEGE-Climat runs at a horizontal resolution T1359 and has 137 vertical levels. These levels are the same as in IFS, and are listed here: <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/UDOC/L137+model+level+definitions>

3.3 The ocean model NEMO v4.2 and sea-ice model SI³

The ocean engine of NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) is a primitive equation model adapted to regional and global ocean circulation problems. It is intended to be a flexible tool to study the ocean and its interactions with the other components of the Earth climate system. Prognostic variables are the three-dimensional velocity field, a non-linear sea surface height, the conservative temperature and the absolute salinity.

The NEMO version used in System 9 is version 4.2 (Madec et al., 2023). In System 9, it runs on the ORCA 0.25° horizontal grid and a vertical resolution of 75 levels. The most important change with respect to previous NEMO versions is the new embedded sea-ice model SI³ (Vancopenolle et al., 2023). The main characteristics of SI³ in System 9 are summarized in Table 2.

Parameterization	SI ³ options for System 9
Number of ice thickness categories	5
Number of ice layers in vertical	2
Number of snow layers	1
Sea-ice dynamics	Adaptive EVP rheology
Minimum ice thickness	0.1
Maximum ice fraction	0.997
Melt ponds computation	Deactivated
Thermal conductivity of snow	0.50
Dry snow albedo	0.87
Melting snow albedo	0.82
Dry ice albedo	0.78
Melting ice albedo	0.65
Specific albedo computation for thin ice	Deactivated

Table 2: Summary of the main characteristics of the SI³ sea-ice model in System 9.

3.4 The surface modeling platform Surfex v8

System 9 uses a surface interface called Surfex, version 8. Surfex (Surface Externalisée, in French) is a surface modeling platform developed by Météo-France, in cooperation with other institutions.

Surfex directly incorporates various physical models for natural land surface (ISBA), river routing (CTRIP) and lakes (FLAKE). It also simulates chemistry and aerosol surface processes. Surfex is designed to provide the atmosphere model with information about the type of surface at the lowest level. In Surfex, each model grid box is represented by three surface types : sea or ocean, freshwater bodies (e.g lakes) and nature (soil and vegetation). Each type is modeled with the corresponding model, and the total flux through the grid box is the sum of the fluxes from all surface types, weighted by their respective fraction.

A detailed presentation of Surfex is available here: <http://www.umr-cnrm.fr/surfex/>

More details on the latest version of Surfex and the ISBA-CTIP land surface and river routing models can be found in Voltaire et al. (2017) and Decharme et al. (2019).

3.5 The coupler OASIS3-MCT v5.0

OASIS is the coupler that manages the exchange of information between the atmosphere model ARPEGE-Climat, the ocean and sea-ice group NEMO-SI³ and the surface platform Surfex. OASIS has been developed at CERFACS since 1991, as a software interface to couple existing ocean and atmosphere numerical General Circulation Models. Its sustained development is ensured by a collaboration between CERFACS and the CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique).

The current OASIS-MCT coupler internally uses MCT, the Model Coupling Toolkit2 (Larson et al. 2005, Jacob et al. 2005), developed by the Argonne National Laboratory in the USA. MCT implements fully parallel regridding and parallel distributed exchanges of the coupling fields, based on pre-computed regridding weights and addresses.

OASIS-MCT is a portable set of Fortran 77, Fortran 90 and C routines. After being compiled, it has to be linked to the component models during their own compilation. Its main function is to interpolate and exchange the coupling fields between them, so that the model components feedback on each other in the course of their integration. Thanks to MCT, all transformations, including regridding, and all coupling exchanges are executed in parallel directly between the component processes via Message Passing Interface (MPI). OASIS-MCT also supports file I/O using NetCDF. To communicate with another component, or to perform I/O actions, a component model needs to include a few specific calls of the Application Programming Interface (API) OASIS MCT coupling library.

Although the OASIS3-MCT version in System 9 is more recent than in previous Météo-France seasonal forecasting system, its implementation remains unchanged from a user perspective.

A more detailed presentation of OASIS is available in Valcke et al. (2021): https://cerfacs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/GLOBC_TR_Valcke_oasis3mct50_2021.pdf

3.6 ECLIS

The ECLIS (Environment for CLimate Simulations) environment is used to define and run the seasonal forecast experiments. ECLIS manages the simulation when it is provided with the necessary information in a single file. The key information are the model binaries and the initial condition files (also called restarts) to be used for each model component, the forcing files, the initial and end dates. The simulation options for each model and for the coupler are also provided as namelists. The binaries are launched together using a MPI message passing software.

3.7 XIOS

The model components of CNRM-CM (ARPEGE-Climat, Surfex, NEMO) embed an output manager called XIOS (Meurdesoif, 2018). XIOS is an input/output parallel server software that enables to write directly the chosen diagnostics of the simulation on NetCDF files during integration. The diagnostics are specified in xml files along with requested post-processing such as time sampling, time averaging, horizontal regriding and vertical interpolation. Consequently, the outputs of System 9 seasonal forecasts are never saved on the native grids of the models, as they are directly produced by XIOS on the requested 1°x1° regular grid for the Copernicus Climate Data Store. More details on the use of XIOS in System 9 are provided in Section 6.3.

3.8 Boundary forcings

Greenhouse gas concentrations in System 9 are yearly global averages from the set of forcings used in CMIP6 experiments. They correspond to the CMIP6 historical forcings up to 2014 (Meinshausen et al., 2017), and to the forcings from the SSP2-4.5 scenario (Meinshausen et al., 2019) from 2015 onwards. Similarly, solar forcings are provided to System 9 as the yearly global averages of total solar irradiance from Matthes et al. (2017). Forcings from volcanic stratospheric aerosols are also the official CMIP6 forcings described in Thomason et al. (2018).

The other necessary forcings are concentrations of tropospheric aerosols and ozone. These forcings come from a preliminary freely-evolving CNRM-CM climate run by Michou et al. (2020), where the interactive aerosol scheme TACTIC_v2 (Michou et al. 2015) and a linear ozone parameterization scheme (Cariolle and Teyssède, 2007) are activated. This run follows the CMIP6 solar, greenhouse gas and volcanic forcings, with historical data up to 2014 and the SSP2-4.5 scenario from 2015 onwards. It provides concentrations of aerosols and ozone that are compatible with the ARPEGE-Climat model used in System 9.

The interest of the Michou et al. (2020) run is to provide an estimate of the long-term evolution of aerosols related to anthropogenic activities. However, it is irrelevant to prescribe the aerosol concentrations in the exact year of the Michou et al. simulation that matches the initialization of the

seasonal forecast: because the simulation is evolving freely, its internal variability has no link to the real-world. Neglecting this aspect might lead, e.g, to applying spatial patterns of aerosols typical of a La Niña year while the actual ENSO phase is El Niño. For this reason, aerosol forcings applied to System 9 correspond to an 11-year moving average from the Michou et al. simulation, such that the long-term trends of aerosols are preserved while their internal variability is smoothed out. Besides, the aerosol concentrations are seasonally-varying to account for changes of aerosol patterns in the course of the seasonal cycle. As an example, aerosol forcings for September 2003 in System 9 seasonal reforecasts are the average of monthly mean aerosol concentrations in the Michou et al. simulation for the month of September between 1998 and 2008 (i.e 11 years centered in 2003).

As for ozone concentrations in System 9, they correspond to a seasonally-varying climatology over the 1995-2014 period from the Michou et al. simulation, e.g ozone concentrations for the month of September are the average of all months of September between 1995 and 2014.

Note that the main difference between System 9 forcings and the previous System 8 is the switch from the SSP3-7.0 scenario to the SSP2-4.5 scenario for all years after 2014, and therefore for the real-time forecasts.

4. Initialization strategy

4.1 Overview

Figure 2: Schematic of the initialization procedure for System 9.

The four model components of System 9 are initialized separately from two data sources: the ERA5 atmospheric reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) for the atmosphere and land surface, and a continuous ocean-only simulation of NEMO v4.2 - SI³, that is designed to output the ocean and sea-ice restarts at the necessary start dates. In order to ensure the realism of these ocean and sea-ice conditions, the oceanic run is prescribed (i.e forced) with atmospheric variables from ERA5 at the surface, and the liquid ocean (NEMO) is nudged in temperature and salinity towards reanalysis data (over the reforecast period) or analysis data (in real time) from Mercator Ocean International.

4.2 ERA5 initial conditions for atmosphere and land surface

The ERA5 files for initialization of the atmosphere are extracted from the Copernicus Climate Data Store in grib format and converted into ARPEGE format with a specific configuration of the ARPEGE model designed for re-processing.

As for the land surface, the Surfex initial conditions are derived from ERA5 surface fields. The required fields are the land-sea mask, the orography, the soil type, the temperature and soil water content of the 4 soil layers available in ERA5, the albedo, the density and temperature of the snow cover, the low and high vegetation cover, as well as the types of high and low vegetation. These fields are similarly retrieved in grib2 data, and are interpolated horizontally and vertically onto the Surfex grid. This procedure requires a Surfex physiographic data file and a land surface database called Ecoclimap, providing an ecosystem classification and a coherent set of land surface parameters. More details on soil moisture interpolation can be found in Boisserie et al. (2016).

4.3 Generation of ocean and sea-ice initial conditions

The initialization run for ocean and sea-ice is a continuous integration of NEMO v4.2 - SI³ over the 1992-present period. In this run, NEMO is strongly nudged (2 days e-folding time) across the 75 model levels towards temperature and salinity fields, upscaled from the Mercator Ocean International GLORYS12V1 reanalysis (GLORYS12V1, 2024). However, no nudging is applied within 225 kilometers of coastlines, nor in the presence of sea-ice. Moreover, both NEMO and SI³ are forced at the surface with hourly values of the following variables from ERA5:

- Near-surface temperature and humidity at 2 m (t2m, q2m)
- 10-m zonal and meridional components of wind (u10, v10)
- Mean sea level pressure (msl)
- Total precipitation (tp) and snowfall (sf)
- Downward surface solar radiation (ssrd) and downward surface thermal radiation (strd)

4.4 Reforecast period (1993-2024)

The ERA5 initial conditions and forcing data are extracted from 1 December 1992 to 31 December 2024 so as to cover the full reforecast period. Similarly, the nudging fields for NEMO are provided by

Mercator Ocean International from the GLORYS12V1 reanalysis over the same period. Unlike the previous Météo-France seasonal forecasting systems, System 9 reforecast extends up to the beginning of the real-time forecast period in early 2025.

4.5 Forecast period (from 2025 onwards)

To avoid discrepancies, initial conditions for real-time forecasts are made with the same initialization strategy as for reforecasts, using data sources that are as similar as possible while being available in near-real time:

- The near-real time reanalysis ERA5T replaces ERA5 for initial conditions of the atmosphere and land surface, but also to drive the forced-nudged ocean run.
- The NEMO nudging files for the forced-nudged ocean run are provided by Mercator Ocean International as daily temperature and salinity fields from the GLO12 operational analysis, upscaled on the ORCA 0.25° grid.

5. Generation of stochastic perturbations

5.1 Introduction

Stochastic dynamics is a methodology of online perturbation of the atmosphere dynamics that consists in adding random past errors of the atmosphere model every day in the course of the simulation. It has been used at Météo-France to generate ensemble seasonal forecasts since System 5 (2015). A detailed description of the technique can be found in Batté and Déqué (2016). The role of stochastic perturbations in the forecasting system is threefold:

- 1) To generate equally probable ensemble members.
- 2) To partly correct the model systematic errors.
- 3) To address rare spurious model simulation failures/crashes, by re-running the simulation with a different set of perturbations.

Three ingredients are necessary to activate the stochastic perturbation system in the re-forecast as well as in the forecast production:

- 1) The perturbation fields.
- 2) The random calendars.
- 3) The definition of the ensembles.

5.2 Generating the perturbation fields

Perturbation fields for stochastic dynamics are generated with a set of preliminary reforecasts during which the model is linearly nudged toward the true trajectory, here the ERA5 reanalysis. These preliminary reforecasts are carried out with the same modeling and initialization options as in System

9. The nudging e-folding time is chosen so as to have a relevant magnitude of model errors. System 9 atmospheric perturbations are generated with a nudging time of 40 days, similar to the previous System 8.

12 pools of perturbations are built for System 9, one for each initialization month. Each pool is based on 31 preliminary nudged reforecasts integrations of 7 months, as we select 31 reforecast years (1993-2023) to generate the perturbations. The last year of the reforecast period (2024) has been excluded to prevent any availability issue in the initial conditions and nudging data at the time of production.

The preliminary nudged reforecasts are as close as possible as a reforecast member starting on the 1st of each month, with three differences:

- 1) The model does not include stochastic perturbations.
- 2) The model is nudged toward 6-hourly ERA5 prognostic variables.
- 3) Every day, the difference ERA5 minus model (i.e error correction term), multiplied by the relaxation factor, is permanently saved in a file for each variable.

Note that because the surface schemes are based on different empirical approaches in ARPEGE-Climat and in ERA5, the relaxation is progressively dampened down to zero in the lowest 31 vertical levels (the lowest 25 levels, from about 1600 m, are not relaxed at all). A symmetrical treatment is applied to the highest 5 levels.

5.3 Random calendar and definition of ensembles

The random choice of a perturbation is done by selecting one of the previously generated error correction terms (ERA5 minus model) verifying the following conditions:

- 1) The perturbation must come from a preliminary nudged reforecast with the same initialization month as the current simulation, e.g the perturbations injected into a March-initialized forecast must come from one of the March-initialized preliminary nudged reforecasts (between 1993 and 2023).
- 2) The perturbation must be an error correction term that occurred during the same lead month as the current month of the simulation.

For instance, the perturbation that is injected in a real-time forecast member initialized on 1 March 2025 while it is simulating the month of May, must be an error that comes from the pool of perturbations for the March initialization (condition 1), and that occurred in May, i.e between 2 and 3 months after initialization (condition 2).

In stochastic dynamics, a new random perturbation is injected every day. Then, apart from the set of initial conditions, one ensemble member is fully defined by the sequence of daily perturbations that are injected from the beginning to the end of the simulation. A sequence of perturbations is defined by calendar files that are initially created randomly, but stored once and for all such that any ensemble member can be reproducible. The calendar files are similarly used for reforecasts and real-time forecasts.

There is one random calendar per lead month (from 1 to 7) and per ensemble member (up to 51). A random calendar is a list assigning each day of the month to a perturbation file. In each calendar, the perturbation file is identified with two random elements:

- 1) The year of initialization of the preliminary nudged reforecast from which the perturbation is drawn (selected randomly between 1993 and 2023).
- 2) The day of the month when the perturbation occurred (selected randomly between 1 and 28, days beyond the 28th of the month are excluded as they do not exist every month).

On the contrary, the calendar month of the perturbation is not predefined in the file: it is a variable that is determined by i) the initialization month of the forecast, and ii) the lead month. As a result, the same random calendar file is used in several forecasts/reforecasts (i.e in all members with the same identification number) but targets a different pool of perturbations depending on the initialization month.

6. Overview of the workflow

This section provides an overview of the workflow for the forecast and reforecast ensemble production.

6.1 Initialization and ensemble generation

A forecast — or reforecast — ensemble is based on individual model integrations initialized with a lagged initialization procedure, i.e. ensemble members are generated in three successive forecast batches as follows:

- The 1st of each month M (reference forecast start date) for Batch 3
- The preceding Thursday in month M-1 for Batch 2
- The second preceding Thursday in month M-1 for Batch 1

The numbering of the batches reflects the chronological order of forecast production, as illustrated in Figure 3 for the case of a 51 member real-time forecast. The list of the start dates for every batch across the reforecast and the real-time forecast periods is predefined in a fixed calendar. Table 3 indicates the numbers of the members produced in each batch, for both reforecasts and real-time forecasts, along with the total ensemble size.

Within a given batch, the forecast members differ by the application of random perturbations during the integration following the stochastic dynamics technique (see Section 5), thus generating the ensemble spread.

Figure 3: Generation of the 51-member ensemble of a System 9 real-time seasonal forecast.

	Batch 1 (Month M-1, 2nd-to-last Thursday)	Batch 2 (Month M-1, Last Thursday)	Batch 3 (Month M, 1st day)	Total ensemble size
Reforecast	Members 017 to 031 (15 members)	Members 002 to 016 (15 members)	Member 001 (1 member)	31
Real-time	Members 027 to 051 (25 members)	Members 002 to 026 (25 members)	Member 001 (1 member)	51

Table 3: Distribution of ensemble members across forecast batches in System 9 lagged initialization procedure.

The initial conditions for ARPEGE and SURFEX are constructed from ERA5(T) following the processing described in Section 4.2. NEMO v4.2 and SI³ are initialized with the forced-nudged ocean run described in Section 4.3.

Prior to the real-time forecast, the forced-nudged run is extended to cover the target start date, using temperature and salinity nudging fields for NEMO from Mercator Ocean International analysis GLO12, and atmospheric forcing fields derived from the ERA5(T) reanalysis. This is done as soon as the ERA5T reanalysis files and the GLO12 files are available, typically two days after the start date of each forecast batch. The last batch (Batch 3, starting on the 1st day of the month) is therefore launched on

the 3rd of the month. In case the ERA5T reanalysis is not available on time for this last batch, it is replaced by the IFS operational analysis so as to ensure a timely delivery of the forecast.

For each initialization month, the corresponding reforecasts between 1993 and 2024 are already available prior to the operational real-time forecast. The main difference with the forecast is the size of the ensemble (31 members instead of 51). In order to maintain the best homogeneity between the real-time forecasts and the reforecasts, the lagged initialization procedure in three batches is applied similarly.

Reforecasts and real-time forecasts are both run on the Météo-France HPC facilities consisting of twin Bull supercomputers: Belenos and Taranis. While reforecasts are produced partly on Belenos and partly on Taranis, the default supercomputer for real-time forecasts is Taranis. Occasional switches of the real-time production on Belenos may occur only if Taranis is unavailable. Note that the supercomputer on which a simulation is run has no impact, because they share the same internal architecture.

6.2 Environment for Climate Simulations (ECLIS)

ECLIS (see Section 3.6) is the set of scripts and tools necessary to run CNRM-CM. It does not include tools for preparing initial nor boundary conditions. An installation script allows to prepare an experiment, and defines another script which actually runs the experiment. ECLIS manages an environment to run CNRM-CM simulations on supercomputers like Belenos and Taranis. It also handles the archiving of restart and output files.

6.3 Post-processing

The XIOS output software (see Section 3.7) manages most of the post-processing of output to the requested C3S format. The inputs to XIOS are sets of xml files for each model component type (AREPEGE, Surfex, NEMO, SI³, CTRIP).

The requested variables are listed in separate xml files for each model component, together with their desired output frequency, vertical levels and horizontal resolution. XIOS can manage operations on model outputs such as time averaging, time slicing, horizontal and vertical interpolation.

XIOS thus generates directly the fields for the atmosphere, surface and ocean on the requested 1°x1° grid with 180 latitudes and 360 longitudes starting at 89.5°S, 0.5°W and extending northwards and eastwards. The data (one file per field and per month) is stored locally on the Météo-France storage server Hendrix and transferred to ECMWF using the ectrans utility.

Tables 4 and 5 list the output variables of System 9. In addition, land-sea mask and surface orography are available.

Every 6 hours	Every 12 hours	Every 24 hours	Every 24 hours, accumulated
Near-surface Air Temperature (tas)	Geopotential Height (zg)	Water Content per Unit Area of Soil Layers (mrlsl)	Liquid Water Equivalent Thickness of Total Precipitation Amount (lwepr)
2m Dewpoint Temperature (tdps)	Air Temperature (ta)	Liquid Water Equivalent Thickness of Snowfall Amount (lweprsn)	Liquid Water Equivalent Thickness of Convective Precipitation Amount (lweprc)
Eastward Near-Surface Wind (uas)	Specific Humidity (hus)	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature (tasmax)	Liquid Water Equivalent Thickness of Surface Snow Amount (lwesnw)
Northward Near-Surface Wind (vas)	Eastward Wind (ua)	Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature (tasmin)	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux (hfls)
Sea Level Pressure (psl)	Northward Wind (va)	Maximum Wind Speed of Gust (wsgmax)	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux (hfss)
Total Cloud Fraction (clt)	At the following 12 pressure levels: 1000, 925, 850, 700, 500, 400, 300, 200, 100, 50, 30, 10 hPa	Snow Density (rhosn)	Subsurface Run-off Amount (mrroab)
Temperature of Soil (tsl)		Snow Area Percentage (snc)	Surface Run-off Amount (mrroas)
Liquid Water Path (cllvi)			Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation (rlds)
Water Vapor Path (prw)			Net Longwave Surface Radiation (rls)
Ice Water Path (clivi)			TOA Net Longwave Radiation (rlt)
Eastward Wind at 100m (ua100m)			Surface Downwelling
Northward Wind at 100m (va100m)			

			Shortwave Radiation (rsds) TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation (rsdt) Net Shortwave Surface Radiation (rss) TOA Net Shortwave Radiation (rst) Snow Area Percentage (snc) Surface Downward Eastward Wind Stress (tauu) Surface Downward Northward Wind Stress (tauv) Liquid Water Equivalent Thickness of Evaporation Amount (lwee)
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Table 4: List of archived atmosphere and land variables.

Every 6 hours	Every 24 hours	Every month
Surface Temperature of Sea Ice (sitemptop) Sea Surface Temperature (tso)	Sea Ice Area Fraction (sic)	Depth of 14 degree Celsius Isotherm (t14d) Depth of 17 degree Celsius Isotherm (t17d) Depth of 20 degree Celsius Isotherm (t20d) Depth of 26 degree Celsius Isotherm (t26d)

		Depth of 28 degree Celsius Isotherm (t28d)
		Depth Average Potential Temperature of Upper 300m (thetaot300)
		Depth Average Salinity of Upper 300m (sot300)
		Sea Surface height Above Geoid (zos)
		Sea Surface Salinity (sos)
		Sea Ice Thickness (sithick)
		Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Sigma Theta 0.01 kg/m3 (mlostheta001)
		Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Sigma Theta 0.03 kg/m3 (mlostheta003)

Table 5: List of archived ocean and sea-ice variables.

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ECMWF – **Robert-Schuman-Platz 3, 53175 Bonn, Germany**

Contact: <https://support.ecmwf.int/>